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1. Plots of k -value against log density of LF larva in Victoria and Zaragosa, Philippines. The solid line is the best fit curve of Bellows' model: $k = aN^b$.

2. Density-dependent mortality (expressed as k -value) of LF due to larval parasitoids in relation to LF larva density. Data are serially linked to show the delayed density dependence.

Attractiveness of light color to selected predators of rice pests

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Light traps are commonly used to monitor insect pest populations in ricefields. We used different colors of light as attractants to rice insect pests in 1988 wet season in Calauan, Laguna, Philippines.

Several insect pests were most attracted to white and yellow lights. And light had the same attraction to various beneficial insects.

Four important predators of rice pests—*Microvelia* sp., *Cyrtorhinus* sp., *Opius* sp., and members of Formicidae family—were collected in significantly higher numbers from the white light trap compared to other light colors tested (see figure). Numbers from yellow, ultraviolet, and green light traps were moderate (see table). Even in traps with the least attractive colors of light (violet, blue, red, and orange), the four predator species were collected.

Spectrometric analysis of the light produced by the eight bulbs tested revealed that not one emitted the pure colors visible to the human eye (see table). Different color combinations, from violet to red, ranging from 4,000 to 7,300 Å, produce the eight colors distinct to human vision.

Among the eight colors of light tested, the light emitted by the white bulb contained the most distinct color bands. These bands were contained in a range from 4,100 to 6,300 Å, which could be the most attractive color combination for the predator species observed in the light traps.

The attraction of the four predator species to white light, coupled with studies on actual predator population, natural mortality, and migratory habits could be used in a rice-pest predator monitoring system. ■

Space limitations prevent IRRN from publishing solely yield and yield component data from fertilizer field trials that are not conducted for at least two cropping seasons or at two differing sites. Publication of work in a single season or at one site is limited to manuscripts that provide either a) data and analysis beyond yield and yield components (e.g., floodwater parameters, microbial populations, soil mineral N dynamics, organic acid concentrations, or mineralization rates for organic N sources), or b) novel ways of interpreting yield and yield component data across seasons and sites.

Select

Color

Ultraviolet
Violet
Blue
Green
Yellow
Orange
Red
White

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Average weekly catches of predators of rice pests in light traps of different colors. IRRI, 1988.

Selected predators caught in different color light traps. IRRI, 1988.

Color	Visible light wavelength range (Å) ^a	Insects (no.)/trap per night ^b			
		<i>Microvelia</i> sp.	<i>Opius</i> sp.	<i>Cyrtorhinus</i> sp.	Formicidae
Ultraviolet	4400-7300	10.31 bc	7.07 b	3.75 c	39.39 b
Violet	4000-5700	5.12 cd	4.81 bc	3.40 d	24.59 cd
Blue	4400-5500	6.71 cd	4.46 c	1.71 dc	21.99 c
Green	4700-6500	9.00 c	8.30 bc	4.21 c	57.34 b
Yellow	5200-6900	14.86 b	9.52 bc	7.18 b	78.72 b
Orange	5600-6700	4.94 d	1.54 d	1.04 de	25.58 d
Red	4300-7300	3.91 d	1.15 d	1.01 e	21.05 cd
White	4100-6300	30.64 a	13.04 a	26.66 a	109.81 a

^aMeasurements done using a Welch Spectroscope. ^bAv of catches over a 10-wk period. In a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT.

Space limitations prevent IRRN from publishing solely yield data and yield component data from routine germplasm screening trials. Publication is limited to manuscripts that provide either a) data and analysis beyond yield and yield components (e.g., multiple or unique resistances and tolerances, broad adaptability), or b) novel ways of interpreting yield and yield component data across seasons and sites.

Pheromone components of rice leaffolders (LF) *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis* and *Marasmia patnalis*

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We measured electroantennogram responses of *C. medinalis* and *M. patnalis* to 20 pheromone standards. Ten µl of 5

mg/ml solutions of each pheromone standard were applied on filter paper and allowed to evaporate for 1 min to remove the solvent.

Responses of males of both species to these stimuli were higher for Z11-16:Ac and Z13-18:Ac (Fig. 1). Female moths did not respond.

Dose-response curves indicate that *M. patnalis* is more sensitive to Z13-18:Ac; *C. medinalis* is more sensitive to Z11-

16:Ac (Fig. 2). Z13-18:Ac was positively identified in the pheromone gland extracts of *M. patnalis*.

It appears that both species use both compounds in their pheromone blends. Species isolation is maintained because of different ratios of the compounds in the pheromone blends.

Based on the EAG responses and the GC-MS analysis of crude extracts of *M. patnalis* pheromone glands, the ratio of Z13-18:Ac and Z11-16:Ac was tenta-